

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B0085
 Date: 10/02/2005
 Take Off: 10:30:07
 Landing: 16:03:23
 Flight Time: 5h33m16

Trials Instructions: AUTEX – Radiative Properties of Mixed Phase Cloud

Operating Area: Radial to the west of the Chilbolton Meteorological Observatory (51° 08' 36" N 01° 26' 02" W), defined by the following points: A - 51° 06' N 1° 35' W B - 50° 55' N 3° 00' W

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Charlie Whitaker	BAe Systems
3	Mission Scientist 1	Dave Kindred	Met Office
4	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
5	Flight Manager (training)	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Dropsondes / CCM2	Steve Devereau	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
9	Cloud Physics (training)	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
10	MARSS	Ian Rule	Met Office
11	Mission Scientist (training)	Dave Pollard	Met Office
12	Journalist	David Shukman	BBC
13	Cameraman	Martin Roberts	BBC
14	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B085 Track 10-FEB-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b085

Date: 10th February, 2005

Project: Mixed Phase

Location: Chilbolton

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
101316		Start posn	0.18 kft	126	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
103007		T/O	2.2 kft	292	From Cranfield
105607	111339	Run 1	4.0 - 4.1 kft	255	A to B
111723	112929	Run 2	3.0 kft	078	B to A
113435	114053	Profile 1	3.1 - 7.0 kft	262	From A, 1000fpm
114101	114224	Profile 1	7.0 - 8.0 kft	262	
114257	114442	Profile 2	7.8 - 6.1 kft	259	
114729	115224	Run 3.1	7.2 kft	259	Freezing level
115552	120730	Run 3.2	7.2 kft	081	B to A
121223	121534	Profile 3	7.2 - 10.0 kft	260	From A
121553	122835	Run 4.1	10.0 kft	260	
123235	124416	Run 4.2	10.0 kft	081	B to A
124952	130027	Profile 4	10.0 - 19.9 kft	257	From A,1000fpm
130028	130431	Run 5.1	19.9 - 20.0 kft	263	
130900	131902	Run 5.2	20.0 kft	068	B to A
132422	133450	Profile 5	20.0 - 30.0 kft	260	From A, 1000fpm
132553		Video	21.4 kft	264	Change tapes
133505	133718	Run 6.1	30.1 - 30.0 kft	266	End at B
134318	135133	Run 6.2	30.0 - 30.1 kft	048	B to A
134828		Sonde	30.0 kft	071	Launch 01
135830	140952	Run 6.3	30.0 kft	264	A to B
140253		Sonde	30.0 kft	265	Launch 02
141513	142411	Profile 6	30.0 - 20.1 kft	073	
143002	143958	Profile 6	20.0 - 10.0 kft	262	
144307	144602	Profile 6	10.1 - 7.3 kft	080	
144653	144948	Profile 6	7.6 - 5.1 kft	072	
145616	151432	Run 7	6.0 kft	262	Freezing level
151808	153122	Run 8	5.1 - 5.0 kft	089	Below freezing lvl
153218		ASPs	5.1 kft	348	Closed
160323		Land	0.16 kft	355	Cranfield
160811		Stop posn	0.16 kft	311	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B085 Track 10-FEB-05

4°W 3°W 2°W 1°W 0°

B085 - Sortie Brief - Radiative Properties of Mixed Phase Cloud – 10/02/05

Trial Objectives:

To characterise the microphysics of mixed phase cloud and atmospheric state in conjunction with Chilbolton Radar Facility

Location:

Runs and profiles are expected to take place along a radial to the west of the Chilbolton Meteorological Observatory (51 08' 36" N 01 26' 02" W), defined by the following points:

A - 51° 06' N 1° 35' W B - 50° 55' N 3° 00' W

Additionally dropsondes will be launched from a point approximately half way along the radial at 2° 7' W.

Weather:

'Reasonably' homogenous mixed phase cloud.

Flight Pattern:

Three levels for runs to be predetermined in addition to min and max levels to lie below, at and above the freezing level within the cloud for runs. These levels may change during flight:

Min : FL030

Level 1: Freezing Level expected at FL060

Level 2: FL100

Level 3: FL200

Max : FL300

	Manoeuvre	Mins
1	[1030]Take off and transit at appropriate level to arrive at point A at FL040	30
2	Run along radial at FL040 From A to B	20
3	Turn and descend to FL030 and perform reciprocal run from B-A	20
4	Turn onto reciprocal heading and profile up to freezing level (FL060 expected) and continue run to point B	20
5	Perform reciprocal run at freezing level from B to A	20
6	Profile up from A to FL100 and continue run to B	20
7	Perform reciprocal run at FL100 B-A	20
8	Profile up from A to FL200 and continue run to B	20
9	Perform reciprocal run at FL200 B-A	20
10	Profile up from A to FL300 and continue run to B	20
11	Perform 2 reciprocal runs at FL300 B-A and A-B dropping sondes at predetermined point on each run.	40
12	Perform profile descent at 1000 ft/min to Freezing level, remaining between points A and B, interrupting as necessary, to finish at point B	30
13	Perform run at Freezing Level B-A	20
14	Recover to Cranfield	30
	Total Sortie time:	330

Communications:

With operators at Chilbolton via SATCOM or VHF radio (127.050 MHz, call-sign "Radsearch").

INCLUDE:

1. An assessment of the flight.
2. Summary of the weather conditions.

A generally successful flight looking at mixed phase clouds in association with Chilbolton Radar, although frontal cloud was significantly thinner and more tenuos than had been forecast.

After T/O from Cranfield at 1030z and transit at mostly FL060, we arrived in the Chilbolton area and set up a series of S & L runs relative to a radial of 260° from Chilbolton out to 60 nm to WSW (about Chard), labelled (A) to (B) i.e. ground positions.

- ① 4000 ft, Run 1 (A) → (B)
 - ② 3000 ft, Run 2 (B) → (A)
- } Below Freezing level, in east of Sc ~~cloud~~ cloud. (As/As above).

Profile 3000' ↗ 8000' @ 1000'/min to investigate Freezing level. (FL)

- ③ Runs 3.1 (A) → (B) & 3.2 (B) → (A) at 7200' at approx Freezing level.
- ④ Profile P3 ↗ up to FL100, then Runs 4.1 (A) → (B) & 4.2 (B) → (A) at 1000' (clear of cloud, or in base of medium level As/As)
- ⑤ Profile (P4) ↗ to FL200, ~~then~~ along track (A) → (B), then Runs 5.1 (A) → (B) & 5.2 (B) → (A). (Generally ^{cloud top} ~~cloud top~~ in thin base of Cs/Cs).
- ⑥ Profile (P5) ↗ FL300, along (A) → (B). Run 6.1 (remainder of leg (A) → (B)) at FL300, then Run 6.2 (B) → (A) Run 6.3 (A) → (B) } with 1 x DROPSIDE EJECTED ABOUT 1/2 WAY POINT OF Run In thin, ^{tenuos} Cs/Cs here (tops > FL350!)
- ⑦ Profile P6 FL300 to 5000' along (A) → (B) / (B) → (A) as staircase descent.
- ⑧ a) Run 7 AT FL060 (A) → (B) INTERSECTING FREEZING LEVEL & } in front of cloud (low)
 b) Run 8 AT 5000' (B) → (A) UNDERNEATH FREEZING LEVEL

We then transited $\sim 5000'$ back to Cranfield; landing at 1604 \neq .

Communications with the Ops room at Chilbolton Radar Observatory were made at regular intervals during the flight via VHF radio link (127.05 MHz) from ATC flight deck, to compare ground / radar based view of cloud conditions / freezing level etc with what was ^{and measured} seen, from the aircraft.

Both Dropsondes (launched on runs 6.2 & 6.3 at FL300) were successfully deployed and gave good 'net' and wind data - the first also provided a very useful (independent) guide to the height of the (sloping) freezing level.

The operating area was to the south of a waving cold front with significant rainfall and more or less continuous frontal cloud in the vertical as forecast. In reality, forecast rainfall totals over S. England were much less than predicted, and hence cloud layers were thinner and more diffuse than expected. Nevertheless, frontal cloud layers were present from $< 3000'$ (lowest run) to well above FL300 (estimated $> FL350$) with gaps between. A good variety of mixed phase, liquid only and solid only particles were noted from Cloud Physics instrumentation. Winds were w'ly (little directional shear) increasing with height. Freezing level initially was about $7200'$, but lowered ~~to~~ ^{during} the sortie to be $\sim 5,500' - 6,000'$ at end (run 7).

Instrumentation worked well (no PCASP). TAFTS / ARIES / SWS not flown due to ^{considerable} clouds / rain expected. No BAe 146 aircraft faults.

NOTE: BBC cameraman + science correspondent (David Shukman) flew aboard this flight - short news item should go out on News at 10 within the next 2 weeks.

DLK, 15/2/05.

Mission Scientist's Log

17.2.20

RADSEARCH
METMAN.

Flight No **B085**.....

Date **10/2/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1024					Start Taxi at Cranfield
1030					T/O Cranfield 230/22kt surface Patches St (2/4) base 1400'. Wind →
					8/8 Sc/As above.
1032	Climb	3500' (Lod)			Med fog on front screen.
1033	CR				Climbing to FL060 (to get A/SC laptop) [Cabin door closed thru' flight BBC onboard] [Some needles seen → C-Physics]
104545	TRANSIT	7.0kft	186°	51.5N 1.4W	Now leveling at 7000' after ~10 mins at FL060 Proceeding towards point A [51.06N 1.35W]
105155					Clearer slot / brighter above
1051					Some droplets (C. Physics) mainly small, some larger. (ALL water)
105400					Turning onto PT(A) now.
105607	START END 1	FL040	263°	51.0N 1.6W	Start Run 1. (A) → (B) 8/8 Sc below. IN GAP HERE ← To NORTH clouds To S. AT THIS LEVEL 8/8 As/Ns above
1102	RUN 1	40 kft	261°	51.0 2.0W	30um water drops (small) ALL WATER going into thicker cloud now here
110420					Limited ice/grapel now on 2D as well as water drops
110630					Thinner cloud here (RFE) (1019 QNH) Nothing seen on 2DC.
110820					Thinner cloud above just ahead
110840					Into cloud gap here.
1112					Cloud thinner here, especially above.
111339	END 2 1.	4.0kft		50.9N 3.0W	END 2 1. Descend to 3000 & turn for reciprocal (B) → (A) Running into Thicker cloud at this level at v. end B 1 & in turn.

[PHI]

PHI

CATHERINE WHITTAKER
ALAN ROBERTS

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.085**.....

Date **10/2/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
111723	RUN 2	3.0kft	071	50.9N 2.9W	Start R2. (B) → (A)
112030					Generally layered cloud above & below Mainly in clear so far this run
112115			→		Into thicker cloud now.
112215			→		Another gap, but cloud encroaching from above/below.
112310			→		Into cloud, 81T turbulence.
					Small water drops (~5µm) So far all run -
					F.L.V. indistinct ^{PARTIAL} 6500'
1128	RUN 2				Larger water drops here Ocn ice crystals here.
112929	END R2	3.0kft	077	51.0N 1.5W	End R2 at point (A). Turn & head back to point (B) to start P1
113435	START P1	3.0kft	290°	51.0N 1.6W	Start P1 ↗ FL070 (approx)
1137		6000'			Clearer now here Temp ~ 0°C
1139		7000'			Continuing to FL080.
					Stop at ~ 7200 (ATC)
1140					Climb FL 070 ↗ FL080 [7,200' [15 F.L.]
114224	END P1				leveling at FL080 [7,000' FL]
114257	START P2				Descent FL080 ↘ FL060 to check Freezing level
114442	END P2	6000'	261	50.9N 2.4W	Freezing level average 7100' ⇒ ^{NEXT LEVEL} 7,200' [FL072]
114729	3.1	7200'	258°	50.9N 2.6W	Start 3.1 at FL072.
					Fairly clear here ^{3/8 S below} (in gap) ^{3/8 AS/C1/Cs above}
115224	END 3.1	7200'	259	50.9N 3.0W	End R3.1 at (B) [Ocn "needles" on 2D in turn, but clearer at this end also clearer above - C1 than to N.]
115552	START 3.2	7200	071°	50.9N 2.9W	(B) → (A).
					INFO. FROM CHILBERTON (VHF CONTACT)
1204.					Still in cloud gap, but thickening ahead. 3/8 S below 3/8 C1/Cs above oat A2/As higher above

NIL FR. LVL INFO CLEAR 5500 SPACE (A)

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Date 10/2/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
120730	END R3-2	7.2kft	076°	51.0nd 1.5W	End R3.2 at (A) Turn & reposition at (A) for P3 → FL100
					[Temp 1 1/2°C warmer over (A) than (B) over Rnd 3:2]
121223	START P3	7.2kft	251°	51.0nd 1.6W	START P3 ↑ 100 at 1000'/min. Still in cloud gap } (DIP in Co by 20 ppt)
121420		8,900ft			Into cloud now (base of thin CM)
121534	END P3 / START P4	10.0kft	261°	51.0nd 1.9W	END P3 / 4.1
121720					Cloud: 5/8 Sc below → into base; 5/8 As/Cs above (at base). Only large wet snow now slowing on 2D.
	CH.				EMIL BOLTON: Cloud patchy over area (A) → (B) thinner to West V's in cloud (base of CM) HAZE
12225					WIND: 283/37KT; 277/18kmp/h ✓ CHECK
12					Cloud thinning now
122835	END R4.1	10.0kft		50.9nd 3.0W	END R4.1 at (B). Turning & heading back at R4.2
123235	START R4.2	10.0kft			Start R4.2 at (B) → (A)
123935	R4.2	10.0kft	076°	51.0nd 2.0W	→ in base of CM - cloud generally thin
124416	END R4.2	10.0kft	076°	51.0nd 1.5W	End R4.2 at A. Turn & reposition at (A) for climb to FL200
					Signal noisy; 2 clear regions 35km → 28000 CLEAR. 70km → 16000 30km
124952	START P4	10.0kft	263°	51.0nd 1.6W	Start Profile P4 ↑ 200 at 1000'/min (A) → (B) Climbing thro thin Ci/Cs.
130028	END P4	20.0kft	261°	50.9nd 2.7W	End P4 (leveling)
(130050)	START R5.1				Start R5.1 until point B Thick Ci/Cs here base of CH
(130431)	END R5.1	20.0kft	260	50.9nd 3.0W	5/8 layers As As Sc below. END R5.1

2D
Larger
1000'/min
WET SNOW
max
2000'/min
Low
CONDENS.

Bloody
Snowy
cliff
1000'/min
20P/20K
Low
CONDENS.

Mission Scientist's Log

FL

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Date **10/2/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
130900	START R5.2	20.0kft	064°	50.9nd 2.9W	Start R5.2 (B) → (A) [Ill-defined Indistinct] Cs/Cs base now hazy & ahead 8/8 Ci
					600-1000 μm } Low conc. ^{ms}
131810			→		Thinner cloud above, Ci, opt blue sky (<1/8)
131902	END R5.2	20.0kft	074°	50.9nd 1.5W	End R5.2. Turn & reposition at (A) before properly ↑ FL300
132422	START PS	20.0kft	260°	51.0nd 1.6W	Start PS ↑ 300 at 1000'/min (A) → (B)
					20km
					CHILBORTON 14000'
					1000'
					W words
133140		27000'	→		Gravel here. In V. thin, tenous Ci/Cs here, still cloud above
133450	END PS / START R6.1	30.0kft	266°	50.9nd 2.7W	End PS & into R6.1 towards (B). In Ci/Cs (thin) but still tenous Ci/above (8/8)
133718	END R6.1	30.0kft	-	50.9nd 3.0W	End R6.1 & turn onto recip. at (B)
1342					Good HALO To STBD with MOCISINS
					→ Presence of Cs
134318	START R6.2	30.0kft	056°	50.9nd 2.8W	START R6.2 (B) → (A) Dropside
1344			070°		8/8 Tenous thin Ci/Cs above & below
134810				51.0nd 2.1W	into thicker cloud ahead
134838	R6.2	30.0kft	071°	51.0nd 2.0W	Dropside EJECTED (#01)
135035			←		Good Met (Wind + Temp data) Thinner cloud ahead
135133	END R6.2	30.0kft	073°	51.0nd 1.5W	End R6.2 Turn & reposition at FL300 for run (A) → (B)
					Tops of Ci/Cs estimated > FL350

Mission Scientist's Log

Dropsonde
FR level
[5400']
[5600']

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
135830	START RG.3	30.0kft	265°	51.0°N 1.5°W	Start Run 6.3 (A) → (B) Dropsonde fail
135935			→		Surface P 1054 mb Dropsonde LANDED.
140253	Dropsonde 2.	30.0kft	265°	51.0°N 2.0°W	Dropsonde #2 REJECTED. [GOOD DATA FR WL 5600']
	Low Conc ^{ns}		Ice / graupel		Still in Ci / Cs (tenuous thin) with 8/6 Ci / Cs above & thin Ci / Cs below.
	CHILDERTON: FR level		(5700')		2km 7000 ↑ ppm 1 3000
				80k ← Tok	
140952	End 6.3	30.0kft		50.9°N 3.0°W	End Run 6.3. Turn & repts ⁿ at (B) for (B) → (A) Rept for deep profile descent at 1000 / min.
141513	START P6	30.0kft	068°	50.9°N 2.8°W	Start P6 at 1000' / min ↓ (B) → (A)
142410	Interrupt P6	to turn	onto	reciprocal	Interrupt P6 at 200.
142802	Restart P6	30.0kft	262°	51.0°N 1.6°W	Recommend P6 FL200 ↓ (A) → (B)
		16.4ft	→		In good cloud gap now 8/6 Ci / Cs above cloud here. 8/6 As / Sc below
143820			←		into thicker cloud now (confirmed by 7 cones on 2D's) (As)
143958	Interrupt P6	10.0kft	261°	50.9°N 2.5°W	Interrupt P6 at FL100.
144130					Thickening As here 2D's 4000um snow/dendrites Confirmed by: Saturated 2DC.
144307	Recomm P6	10.0kft	082°	50.9°N 2.5°W	Recommend P6 to FL050.
1446					Conflicting Air Traffic
144655					Interrupt P6 at FL073, then ↑ FL075
					Recommend P6 ↓ from FL075
					Still in thicker cloud / Sc now.
144948	End P6	5.0 kft	074°	51.0°N 1.6°W	End P6 at FL050, Turn & climb to FL060 for pt (A)

Increase in
Pollutⁿ
CO.
FL100
↓
FL070

Mission Scientist's Log

lower w. end. 5700'

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
145616	R7	6000ft	261°	51.0°N 1.6W	Start R7. (A) → (B)
				Chilberton	v. scrappy; cold front not yet arrived
				Leisr	3 mis: Wet snow → needle / grasped along this run
		Temp reducing		as head	(A) → (B) but leveling (A) → (B) (FL)
				ie. Slapping	freezing level
		Slapping down as head w. clouds (ie. CONDENSED)			This could be v. interesting run to analyse. 8/8 AcAs above; 7/8 Sc/St below.
151130		into cloud gap		2D	Cond ¹ reduced. Mxt phase.
		8700ft		8/8 Ac/Cs above 7/8 Sc below	
151432	End R7	6000ft	259°	50.8°N 3.0W	End R7. Turn & descend to 5000' for final run (B) → (A)
151808	Start R8	5000ft	579°	50.9°N 2.9W	Start R8 (B) → (A)
153122	End R8	5000ft	062	51.1°N 1.5W	End of run at A above Sc 8/8 Air temp. 0°C at start of run dropping to -1°C at end
		END OPS			
16:04					Land Cranfield [Sh 34m]
16:08					end of text
16:09					Shut down
					Fuel: 590 + 750 = 1340

FLIGHT NUMBER	B085	DATE:	10/2/04	OPERATOR:	Ruth Purvis		
PROJECT: AUTEX							
T/O	10:31:42	ASP open	10:35	ASP closed	15:35	Land	

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	Yes
All cylinders pressures are OK	Yes
Ozone Span = 514, Offset = 50	Yes

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	30	160	150
POST FLIGHT	22	160	150

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
0.5	0.5	1.441	Set to 0	N/A
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
9:26 Identical	34	1.21	7.14	

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS

O3 inlet was not connected – must have been from when it was taken off last week this was reconnected

For some reason the CO lamp gas flow was fluctuating which affected the lamp temp, this meant lamp had not warmed up by take off

FLIGHT NUMBER	B085	DATE:	10/2/04	OPERATOR:	Ruth Purvis		
PROJECT: AUTEX							
T/O	10:31:42	ASP open	10:35	ASP closed	15:35	Land	

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL	Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)
	24/1/05	89.71	72.11	6469.47

Time	Flight Level	CO						
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
10:43:33	060	93.06	76.90	7156.04	49.45	7.14		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)						
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		34	-	-	1.190	0	-	
Time	Flight Level	CO						
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
10:56:11	040	91.56	78.66	7201.76	50	7		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)						
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		34	-	-	-	-	-	
Time	Flight Level	CO						
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
11:17:47	030	90.49	79.07	7155.11	50	7		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)						
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		34	-	-	1.208	-	-	
Time	Flight Level	CO						
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)		
11:49:43	070	90.14	78.69	7093.08	50	7		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)						
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample	
		34	-	-	-	-	-	

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

FLIGHT NUMBER	B085	DATE:	10/2/04	OPERATOR:	Ruth Purvis		
PROJECT: AUTEX							
T/O	10:31:42	ASP open	10:35	ASP closed	15:35	Land	

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
12:21:29	100	89.37	79.72	7124.20	50	6.81	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		-	-	1.187	0.006	-	
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
13:03:15	200	87.87	88.16	7746.24	50	5.48	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		-	1.0	1.0	1.181	0	-
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
-	300	83.55	116.25	9712.13	50	5.36	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		-	-	-	-	-	-
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
-	100	89.99	80.09	7207.21			
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
14:55:06	060	90.51	80.69	7303.25	50	-	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		-	-	-	-	-	-

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT NUMBER	B085	DATE:	10/2/04	OPERATOR:	Ruth Purvis		
PROJECT: AUTEX							
T/O	10:31:42	ASP open	10:35	ASP closed	15:35	Land	

GENERAL COMMENTS

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B085

Date: 10/2/05

Operator: papj

Page 1 of 7

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
											Run start @ 040
1057											
1058					120	150	12				
1059					350	200	12				
1100					100	100	12				
1101					20	50	12				
1102					400	200	10				
1103					200	200	10				
1104					200	200	10				
1105					400	200	10				
1106											
1107											
1108											
1109											
1110											
1111											
1112											
111339											End of run 1
111723											Start run 2 @ 030
1118											
1119					80	50	10				
1120					50	100	12				
1121											
1122											
1123					10	50	12				
1124					20	50	12				
1125											
1126					150	250	1/11				
1127					200	200	11/12				
1128					200	200	11/12				
1129					100	150	11/12				
112929											

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B085

Date: 10/2/05

Operator: papj

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
113435											Start p1 @ 030
113541					100	100	11/12				040
1136					200	100	11/12				050
1137											060
114224											End p1 @ 080
114257											Start p2 @ 080
114345											070
114442											060 end p2
114729											Start run 3 @ 072
1148											
1149											
1150											
1151											
115224											End run 3.1
115552											Start run 3.2
1156					10	300	6				
1157											
1158											
1159											
1200											
1201											
1202											
1203											
1204											
1205											
1206											
120730											End 3.2

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B085

Date: 10/2/05

Operator: papj

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
121223											Start p3 @ 072
121324											080
121430											090
121534											End p2
121553											Start run 4.1 @ 100
1216											
1217											
1218					10	600	2				
1219					10	600	2				
1220					10	800	2				
1221					10	800	2				
1222					10	800	2	150	1000	2	
1223											
1224											
1225					50	600	5/6	500	1000	2	
1226					10	600	2				
1227											
122835											End run 4.1
123235											Start run 4.2
1233											
1234											
1235											
1236					50	100	11/12				
1237					50	800	2	500	1000	2	
1238					20	800	2	1000	1000	2	
1239					20	800	2	2000	1000	2	
1240					20	600	2	2000	1000	2	
1241					10	600	2	1000	1000	2	
1242					10	600	2		1500	2	
1243											
1244											
124416											End run 4.2

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B085

Date: 10/2/05

Operator: papj

Page 4 of 7

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
124952											Start p4 @ 100
125050					500	200	2				110
125150					50	200	10				120
125256											130
125356											140
125510					10	400	10				150
125614					10	800	3				160
125721					10	800	3	1000	1000	3	170
125819					10	800	3	1000	1000	3	180
125925					10	600	3	1000	1000	3	190
											200 end p4
130028											Start run 5.1
1301					10	800	3	2000	1000	3	
1302					10	800	3	2000	1000	3	
1303					10	800	3	4000	1000	3	
1304					10	800	3	2000	1000	3	
130431											End run 5.1
1309											Start run 5.2
1310					10	800	3	800	1000	3	
1311					20	600	3	2500	1000	3	
1312					20	800	3	1500	1000	3	
1313					20	500	3				
1314					20	500	3	6000	1000	3	
1315					20	600	3				
1316					20	600	3				
1317					20	60-0	3	6000	800	3	
1318					20	600	3				
131902											End run 5.2
132422											Start p5 @ 200
132530					10	600	3				210
132634					10	600	3				220
132740											230
132841											240

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B085

Date: 10/2/05

Operator: papj

Page 5 of 7

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
132950											250
133045					20	200					260
133147					20	200					270
133245					20	200					280
133343					20	200					290
133450											Start run 6.1
1337											
133718											End run 6.1
134318											Start run 6.2 @ 300
1345					10	200	10				
1346					50	200	10				
1347					50	150	10				
1348					50	150	10				
1349					50	150	10				
1350					50	150	10				
1351					50	150	10				
135133											End run 6.2
135830											Start run 6.3 @300
1359					20	150	11				
1400											
1401					20	100	10				
1402											
1403											
1404					5	100	10				
1405					10	100	10				
1406					10	400	3				
1407					10	400	3				
1408					20	400	3				
1408					20	400	3				
140952											
											End run 6.3

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B085

Date: 10/2/05

Operator: papj

Page 6 of 7

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
141513											Start p6 @ 300
141613					20	200	10				290
141711					10	600	4				280
											220
142417											200
1433					10	800	3				170
143350											160
143448											150
143544					10	800	3	3000	1000	3	140
143645											130
143750					40	800	3	300	3000	3	120
144416					30	800	6	5000	4000	3	090
144520					40	700	6	2000	4000	3	080
144741					50	800	3	2000	2000	3	070
144849					20	400	3	800	2000	3	060
144948											End of p6 @ 050
145616											Start run 7.1 @ 050
1458					20	400	3	800	3000	3	
1459					20	800	3	800	3000	3	
1500					20	800	3	1000	3000	3	
1501					20	800	6	1000	3000	3	
1502					50	400	6				
1503					50	600	4				
1508											
1511											
1512											
1513											
151432											End run 7

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	10/02/05	Flight	B085	log pages
Operator(s)	Ian Rule		Campaign	Mixed Phase (Chilbolton)		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection	tick					
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers	tick					
Close all MARSS circuit breakers	tick					
FERA on						at time 0815 ish
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on						at time 0815 ish
Initial target temperatures	Hot	ambient	Cold	The same		
Target heating						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Scanning on (LMD box)						at time 0815 ish
Scan indication	Monitor	tick	Visual	tick		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software						at time
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud	8/8 SCu	Precip	Light dz		
	Surface	damp	Pressure	1006		
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} + 0$		at time 0920		
Brightness temps 'sensible'					
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344	Cold	286
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)
	42	35	38	38	42

Power changeover

Headset on before start						
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again						at time

Flight #	B	Date	Operator(s)	log page	2	of	2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks	Sys			
103008			T/o				
105607	R1	FL040	From A to B in thick cloud, occasional layers seen				
1103			Laptop time check = DRS minus 1s				
1105			Between cloud layers (in/out)				
111339			End run, position B				
111723	R2	FL030	B to A				
112929			End run point A				
113435	P1	FL030	Start Profile up to above freezing level from point A				
114224		FL080	End Profile				
114257	P2	FL080	Start profile				
114442	P2	FL060	End profile				
114729	R3.1	FL072	Start run				
115224	R3.1	FL072	End run				
115552	R3.2	FL072	Start run B to A				
120730			End run				
121223	P3	FL072	Profile up				
121534	P3/R4.1	FL100	End profile/start run				
122835	R4.1	FL100	End run				
123235	R4.2	FL100	Start run B to A				
124416	R4.2	FL100	End run				
124952	P4	FL100	Profile up				
130028	P4/R5.1	FL200	End profile/start run 5.1				
130431	R5.1	FL200	End 5.1				
130900	R5.2	FL200	Start run 5.2, B to A				
131902	R5.2	FL200	End run				
132422	P5	FL200	Start profile up A to B				
133450	P5	FL300	End profile				
133450	R6.1	FL300	Start run				
133718	R6.1	FL300	End run				
134318	R6.2	FL300	Start run				
134530	R6.2	FL300	Marssmon dropped out				
1346			MARSSmon back up				
1350	R6.2	FL300	Time check, laptop 4s slower than DRS				
135133	R6.2	FL300	End run				
135830	R6.3	FL300	Start run				
140952	R6.3	FL300	End run				
141513	P6	FL300	Profile down				
144948	P6	FL050	End profile				
155616	R7	FL060	Start run A to B				
151432	R7	FL060	End run				
151808	R8	FL050	Start run B to A				
153122	R8	FL050	End run/end science				
1537			Time check laptop 4-5s slower than DRS time				
1538			Stop recording on laptop				
1539			MARSS pc stop recording				
1540			Time check MARSS pc – 10s faster than DRS				
160322			Land Cranfield				

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B085**

Date: 10/02/05

FAAM © 2004

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	Y	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann		Y	SID 2	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP100	N	
G. Eastern		Y	CIP 2	N	
J. Williams		Y	CPI	N	
Nevzorov		Y	HVPS		
TWC		Y	<u>Racks:</u>		
FWVS	N		INC	N	
<u>Radiometers</u>			CCN / CNC	Y	N
Upper Clear	N		CVI	Y	N
" Red	N				
" Silicon	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
" JO1D	N		PSAP	Y	N
Lower Clear		Y	Nephelometer	Y	N
" Red		Y	Filters	Y	N
" Silicon		Y	AMS	Y	N
" Clear		Y	VACC	Y	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			LTI	Y	N
TAFTS	Y	N			
MARSS	Y	Y			
DEIMOS	Y	Y			
ARIES	Y	N			
SWS	Y	N			
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone		Y			
ECGC	N				
NOX		Y			
CO		Y	<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC	Y	N			
PAN	Y	N			
PERCA	Y	N			
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B085

Date: 10/02/05

Instruments

1. AVAPS – pc not receiving HORACE data. Reset PC then okay.
2. HORACE display – Flt. Manager's laptop display of temperatures & altitude plotting "old" data in graph but showing current values at top of display. Replotted a couple of times then okay.
3. Fltsumm – where does the time stamp come from?
4. Inboard VCR – keeps going into standby mode. Still recording okay though.

Aircraft

1. Intercom – Co very quiet and A/c Scientist loud compared to other comms.

10/2/05
FORECAST
1200 z
(MESOSCALE
MODEL)

Infrared 10 Feb 2005 0730 UTC

SSFM weather summary for S00003746 for 10/02/2005

TOPS
FL 380
FREEZING
level
6000'

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B085:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting processing completion

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	02 Oct 2006	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Rear/Downward Facing Cameras

8mm video recordings from this flight reside with :

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